

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 3, No. 7; July 28, 1997

Dear Readers:

In this issue of J.UCS you will find four interesting papers covering a wide spectrum of interests.

Maybe it is important to point out once more that J.UCS now offers a novel feature which enables the readers to easily annotate existing contributions WITHOUT effecting the contributions as such. Thus, you can add remarks to papers that have been written before by yourself or someone else, and those remarks can include links to earlier papers in J.UCS, or to papers that have appeared later, or to any other WWW sites! Note that you can also add remarks to remarks, so anyone can now start a "discussion" about any contribution in J.UCS. Please make use of this facility to create, based on J.UCS, a fully hyper-linked network of scientific material.

Yours cordially,

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu

P.S.: The official text that we are sending out in this respect is the following:

Dear J.UCS Editor and Reader:

We would like to inform you of a new and important feature of J.UCS.

J.UCS is now probably the first major refereed journal that makes it possible for readers to add comments ("annotations") to all contributions, including previous comments. This offers the possibility for "asynchronous discussions", for notes for other readers, and much more, including links to other material.

How to register:

1. First you have to go to J.UCS home page at the following URL <http://www.iicm.edu/jucs>
2. click on "Discussion Forum" at the bottom right corner of the page
3. to get the password click on "register now"
4. Enter your email address
5. click "Register now"
6. in a few seconds you will receive your password by email

7. go to the J.UCS home page
8. click on the "Identify" button. You can now either change your password or use the one you have received

In this connection, let me point out that J.UCS is based on Hyperwave. More information on Hyperwave can be found under <http://www.hyperwave.com> or <http://www.iicm.edu/hyperg>.

Note that whatever you write as annotation must be the body of an HTML page. Thus it can be basically plain ASCII text, but to start a new line insert `
`, to start a new paragraph insert `<P>` and to create a link to some other place use the standard HTML markup, i.e. `clickable text` if you want that the "clickable text" when clicked on leads to the URL specified.

(For more information on HTML you may want to consult:

- <http://www.w3.org/MarkUp/>
- <http://www.boutell.com/faq/>
- <http://www.ncsa.uiuc.edu/General/Internet/WWW/HTMLPrimer.html>)

Please note also that the annotations in J.UCS are as "stable" as the contributions, i.e. neither the contents of the document annotated nor your own annotations will change in the future.

Hope you will enjoy and use this new feature!

Cordially,
The J.UCS team in Graz/Austria